

Supplementary Materials for

CRISPR/Cas-mediated heritable chromosome fusions in *Arabidopsis*

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The PDF file includes:

Materials and Methods

Figs. S1 to S9

Tables S1 to S6

Other Supplementary Materials for this manuscript include the following:

Data S1 to S4

Materials and Methods

Cloning of T-DNA constructs.

Cloning of the transfer DNA (T-DNA) constructs was based on the Gateway-compatible (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., <https://www.thermofisher.com>) entry vectors pEn-Sa-Chimera (44) or pEn-RZ-LbChimera (45) and destination vectors pDe-Sa-Cas9 with *S. aureus* Cas9 (pDe-Sa-Cas9(44)/pDe-Sa-Cas9 EC (25)) or pDe-ttLb-Cas12a with an engineered variant of the *Lachnospiraceae* bacterium Cas12a (23) (pDe-ttLb-Cas12a (23)/pDe-ttLb-Cas12a EC (46)) under the control of an ubiquitin or egg cell-specific (EC) promoter. The spacer sequences (Table S1) were cloned as annealed oligonucleotides into the respective individual entry vectors via BbsI restriction digest. If only one guide RNA (gRNA) cassette was used, it was integrated into the respective destination vectors via Gateway LR reaction. If two gRNAs were combined in one construct, the first gRNA cassette was integrated into the respective destination

vectors via MluI restriction digest and the second gRNA cassette transferred via a Gateway LR reaction. The plasmid used to induce the second arm transfer in line F8 was additionally modified by first integrating both gRNA cassettes into pDe-Sa-Cas9 EC, removing the SaCas9 ORF by restriction digest with Ascl, exchanging the phosphinothricin (PPT) resistance cassette with a kanamycin resistance cassette (amplified from pDe-Sa-Cas9 (44) using primers oMR899 and oMR900, Table S4) via restriction digest with HindIII and then integrating the ttLb-Cas12a-i ORF (amplified from pDe-ttLbCas12a-I (24) with primers oMR577 and oMR752, Table S4) into the plasmid via Ascl restriction digest. The plasmid used to induce the second arm transfer in line T8 was additionally modified by first integrating both gRNA cassettes into pDe-Sa-Cas9 EC, removing the SaCas9 ORF by restriction digest with Ascl and exchanging the PPT resistance cassette with a hygromycin resistance cassette (amplified from pDU.GUS (47) using primers oMR790 and oMR791, Table S4) via restriction digest with HindIII. For analysis of Sanger sequencing data of the constructs, the software ApE (v3.1.5) was used.

Plant material, growth conditions and transformation.

Experiments were performed in the *Arabidopsis thaliana* background Columbia-0 (Col-0) and the TDNA insertion line *ku70-1* (At1g16970, SALK_123114) (48), obtained from the SALK collection (49). In addition, the *A. thaliana* ecotype Landsberg erecta (Ler-1) was used for crossing for the determination of crossover (CO) frequencies. For cultivation in the greenhouse, plants were grown on a substrate containing 1:1 Floraton 3 (Floragard Vertriebs GmbH) and Vermiculite (2-3 mm, Deutsche Vermiculite Dämmstoff GmbH). For cultivation under axenic conditions, seeds were sown on agar plates containing germination medium (4.9 g l⁻¹ Murashige and Skoog medium, 10 g l⁻¹ saccharose, pH 5.7 and 7.6 g l⁻¹ plant agar) and placed in a growth chamber. Cultivation took place at 22 °C with a 16 h:8 h light:dark cycle. For sterile plant culture, the seeds were surface sterilized with 4% sodium hypochlorite and stratified overnight at 4 °C. For propagation, the plants were cultivated in the greenhouse under 16 h light:8 h dark conditions at 22 °C for 6-7 weeks until seed set. Agrobacterium-mediated floral dip transformation (50) was performed using 4-5 week-old plants. The transformed plants were cultivated for 4-5 weeks until seed set. T1 plants were propagated in the greenhouse and the seeds harvested. T1 seeds were stratified and sown on germination medium including the respective herbicide, either PPT (0.006 g l⁻¹), gentamicin (0.06 g l⁻¹), kanamycin (0.03 g l⁻¹) or hygromycin (0.01 g l⁻¹), and cefotaxime (0.5 g l⁻¹) and 80 plants randomly picked for propagation. T2, T3 or T4 seeds were randomly picked and sown on germination medium without further additives. The plates were placed in a growth chamber for 2 weeks.

DNA extraction for PCR screenings and recombination analysis.

For individual plant screenings, plants were randomly numbered and one leaf per T2 plant was cut off and separately placed into a 1.5 ml reaction tube. For bulk screenings, one leaf each from 40 randomly numbered T2 plants was cut off and leaves combined in the same 1.5 ml reaction tube. The DNA was extracted as described previously (21). Sample size for PCR screenings was determined based on previously detected translocation frequencies of 0.1% in *Arabidopsis thaliana* Col-0 and 0.5% in the *ku70* mutant background (5).

Establishment of the homozygous F8 and T8 lines

The T2 bulk DNA pools were screened for the presence of the chromosome arm translocations via PCR using junction-specific primers (Table S4). The individual plants of positively tested lines were then subjected to individual DNA extraction to identify the individual plants harboring the rearrangements. The individual DNA samples were again screened by PCR. The identified positive plants were transferred to the greenhouse and grown for 6–7 weeks until seed set. In the T3 generation, the plants were

genotyped by PCR using primers specific for the WT and translocation junctions (Table S4) and homozygous plants transferred to the greenhouse and grown for 6–7 weeks until seed set.

PacBio sequencing and structural variant analysis.

Genomic DNA was extracted from 1.5 g of ground tissue from 3-week-old seedlings using the NucleoBond HMW DNA kit (MACHEREY-NAGEL GmbH & Co. KG, Düren, Germany), following the manufacturer's protocol. DNA quantity was assessed using a Qubit fluorometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). Samples were sent to Bioscientia Healthcare GmbH (Ingelheim, Germany), where additional purification was performed with the DNeasy PowerClean Pro Cleanup Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany), followed by library preparation and long-read sequencing on the PacBio Revio platform using Revio SMRT Cells (for QUASt report see Data S3). For chromosome 3 of line F8, a total of 253,288 subreads were generated, with an average read length of 11,587 bp, a mean sequencing depth of 52.97×, and a genome coverage of 98×. For chromosome 1 of line T8, 411,379 subreads were produced, with an average read length of 8,248 bp, a depth of 74.06×, and coverage of 99×. Chromosome 5 of line T8 yielded 350,327 subreads, with a mean depth of 74.43× and a coverage of 100×. Long reads were aligned to the Col-CEN reference genome (51) using Minimap2 (52) (v2.28). Structural variants (SVs) were identified using Sniffles2 (53) (v2.6.2; Data S1) with default parameters. The resulting VCF file containing SV calls was further validated through manual inspection using the Integrative Genomics Viewer (54).

De novo genome assembly and Circos visualization.

Custom reference genomes, based on the Col-CEN assembly (51), were created using custom Python scripts to include the anticipated chromosomal rearrangements leading to the generation of the 8 chromosome lines as well as the T-DNA sequences present in the plant genomes that were used to induce the translocations in order to be able to verify any off-target rearrangements detected due to the presence of the T-DNAs. In addition, in the custom reference genome of line T8, a reciprocal translocation between chromosome 1, position 5,808,429, and chromosome 2, position 20,479,095, was included that was already present in the *ku70* mutant line that was used as genetic background for the creation of line T8 and was therefore also present in line T8. High-fidelity (HiFi) PacBio reads were *de novo* assembled into contigs using Hifiasm (55). These raw reads were then aligned back to the assembled contigs to generate a PAF file, which was subsequently converted into an overlap file for polishing. Polishing was performed using Racon (56), incorporating the overlaps file and the original HiFi reads to generate a consensus sequence. This Racon-polished assembly was then used as the query in RagTag (57) (correct mode), with the custom-engineered reference genomes and PacBio validation reads as input. The corrected contigs were further scaffolded using RagTag's scaffold function against the same engineered reference genomes. The final scaffolded assembly (for QUASt report see Data S4) was aligned to the reference using NUCmer (58) (parameters: -l -s), producing a delta file. This alignment file was filtered with delta-filter (parameters: -c -H -l 75.0 -l -L 5000 -r -T) to retain only alignments ≥ 5 kb in length and $\geq 75\%$ identity. The filtered delta file was then converted to a tabular format using show-coords (same parameters), which was subsequently imported into RStudio (R version 4.2.2, Rstudio version 2023.03.0+386). Structural comparisons and genome links were visualized using the circlize package.

Chromosome spread preparation.

Closed flower buds of about 1 mm in length were collected and preserved for 48 hours at room temperature (RT) in a fresh fixative solution (3:1 v/v, ethanol: glacial acetic acid). Chromosome spreads were prepared and stained as described previously (59), with a minor modification of reducing the

enzyme digestion time to 60 min. The DAPI-stained chromosome spreads were checked to study the behavior of meiotic chromosomes or find well-spread mitotic chromosomes for further fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH) analysis.

FISH.

Single-copy oligo FISH probes were designed using proprietary software from Abor Bioscience (Ann Arbor, MI, USA). 45 bp-long single-copy sequences were used for the probe design, and genomic regions of approximately 100 kb were chosen either up- [blue color] or downstream [magenta color] of the CRISPR/Cas-induced break points (Table S5). Additionally, BAC probes specific to chromosome 1 [yellow color] (F22L4 and T1N6 for short arm; F5I6 and T21F11 for long arm) and 5 [green color] (F7J8, T10O8, F7A7, T20L15, T7H20, T1E22) were used in different combinations with single-copy oligo FISH probes (Table S5). BAC plasmid DNA was extracted using the QIAGEN Large-Construct Kit (Cat No. 12462) and labeled with the nick translation kits Atto647N or Atto550 (Jena Bioscience, Germany). The FISH was carried out as described previously (60). At least two independent experiments were carried out to confirm the reproducibility of the labeling patterns.

Immunostaining.

Young leaves were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (freshly made from a 37% stock solution) in Tris buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.5, 10 mM Na₂-EDTA, 100 mM NaCl, 0.1% TritonX-100, pH 7.5) on ice for 5 min under vacuum conditions in a concentrator (5301, Eppendorf) following 25 min without vacuum condition. Then, the samples were washed twice in 1x PBS buffer (137 mM NaCl, 2.7 mM KCl, 10 mM Na₂HPO₄, and 1.8 mM KH₂PO₄) for 5 min. Afterwards, leaf nuclei were isolated using the chromosome isolation buffer LB01 (61). Isolated nuclei were filtered through a 35 µm nylon mesh with subsequent centrifugation onto microscopic slides with Cytospin3 (Shandon) at 400 rpm for 5 min. The immunostaining procedure was followed as described previously ((62) with the primary antibody against *A. thaliana* CENH3 (ab72001, Abcam, Cambridge, UK) with 1:2000 dilution factor and secondary antibody anti-rabbit Alexa 488 (1:100 diluted, 711-545-152, Jackson ImmunoResearch, UK).

Microscopy.

Images were acquired in grey scale using an epifluorescence microscope (Olympus BX61) equipped with a cooled charge-coupled device (CCD) camera (Orca ER; Hamamastu), and were pseudocolored with Adobe PHOTOSHOP CS (Adobe Systems).

RNA-seq.

Total RNA was extracted from 100 mg of ground two week-old seedlings, following the protocol of the Quick-RNA Miniprep kit (Zymo Research, Rezzato, Italy). Three replications were considered for each line. The RNA was sent to BGI (Poland) for library preparation and sequencing using the DNBseq PE150 platform. A total of 40 million reads was generated for each sample. The bioinformatics analyses of data were conducted using the Dr Tom network platform provided by BGI (<http://report.bgi.com>). Adapter sequences were trimmed using SOAPnuke. Subsequently, the clean data were aligned to the reference genome of *A. thaliana* (51) using HISAT2 (63). Differential expression analysis was performed between the 8-chromosome lines and the WT using the DESeq2 package (64) with a significance threshold of Q-value ≤ 0.01 and an absolute log₂ fold change ($|\log_2FC|$) ≥ 2 . Furthermore, the annotated genes were subjected to KEGG pathway enrichment analysis to elucidate their functional significance (65).

Phenotyping and root measurement.

Seeds were sown on a substrate containing 6:1 Klasmann TS 3 (Klasmann-Deilmann GmbH) and silica sand (0.8-1.2 mm, MB Mineral s.r.o., Prague, Czech Republic) and vernalized for 2 days in a cold room (4 °C) and then transferred to phytotrons and grown under long-day conditions (16 h light, 100 mmol m⁻²s⁻¹, 21 °C; 8 h dark, 19 °C), while randomly distributed within the cultivation boxes. During the next 3 weeks, the phenotype of plants was monitored seven times (9, 11, 14, 15, 17, 21 and 22 days after sowing) by the PlantScreen™ Compact System (PSI, Drásov, Czech Republic). The images were preprocessed using the PlantScreen™ Data Analyzer software to extract RGB-imaging-based parameters. Morphological data were visualized and analyzed through PCA using the R packages factextra (66), tidyverse (67) and plotly (68). For single screen PCA plots, the differences between the respective plant lines were presented as centroids with ellipses representing 95% confidence interval. For root length analysis, seeds were ethanol-sterilized and germinated in phytotrons for seven days on ½ Murashige and Skoog medium (Duchefa, Biochemical, Haarlem, The Netherlands) supplemented with 0.8% plant agar (Duchefa) under long-day conditions (16 h light, 100 mmol m⁻²s⁻¹, 21 °C; 8 h dark, 19 °C). Roots of 7-day-old seedlings were measured with the ImageJ software (69). Data distribution was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test for normality. As the assumption of normality was violated ($p < 0.05$), the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test with Dunn's post-hoc comparison test with the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) were used for data evaluation. The statistical evaluation was done using the software Origin(Pro), Version 2023 (OriginLab Corporation, Northampton, MA, USA). For advanced automated phenotypic analysis of Arabidopsis seeds, a seed aliquot was used to ensure uniform distribution within the analyzed sample. 4,037 (Col-0), 3,970 (F8 line), and 3,719 (T8 line) seeds (independent biological replicates) were phenotyped. Seeds were collected from two independently grown plants of each line. Imaging was performed at 0° and 90° projections using the Boxeed 2.1 instrument (Boxeed 2.1, Labdeers s.r.o.) and the average value from both projections was used to characterize the seed phenotype. Data were processed using Origin(Pro), Version 2023 (OriginLab Corporation, Northampton, MA, USA).

Fertility assays.

Homozygous, heterozygous and Col-0 plants were grown in the greenhouse for 5-6 weeks under 16 h light/8 h dark conditions at 22 °C. Ten randomly numbered mature siliques of nine or ten randomly numbered plants per line were collected and incubated for 2 days in 70% EtOH to determine the effects of the chromosome number reductions on fertility. The number of seeds per silique was counted using a binocular microscope. To verify the normal distribution of the data, the Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted. In line F8, the data from the Col-0 and heterozygous plants were normally distributed ($p > 0.05$), while the data from the homozygous plants were not ($p < 0.05$). In line T8, the data from the Col-0 and homozygous plants were normally distributed, while that of the heterozygous plants were not. Therefore, a two-sided Mann-Whitney U test was used to analyze the differences between the groups and calculate the P values. The data were normalized to the mean seed count of Col-0, which was set to 100%. Boxplots were created using R Studio (Version 2024.04.1 Build 748) and CorelDRAW 2022 Graphics Suite (Version 24.0.0.301).

Determination of CO frequency.

Homozygous plants and, as a control, Col-0 or *ku70* plants, respectively, were crossed with the Ler-1 ecotype for subsequent determination of CO frequencies. F1 seeds were propagated in the greenhouse and ripe F2 seeds were harvested after 6-7 weeks. The CO frequency was determined by the detection of marker changes via SNP-based genotyping using cultivar-specific probes in DNA samples of 400

randomly numbered F2 plants per line. For chromosomes 1 and 5, 16 and 15 TaqMan probes and specific primers were designed, respectively. For chromosome 3, 14 TaqMan assays were designed. Additionally, 8 TaqMan assays were designed for the long arm of chromosome 4 which served as a control. Only the fused chromosome arms of lines F8 and T8 were analyzed. All probes and primers are listed in Tables S4 and S6. The analysis was performed using a Lightcycler 480 II (Roche, Basel, Switzerland) and the PerfeCTa qPCR ToughMix (Quantabio, Beverly, MA, USA) according to the manufacturer's protocol but with a total reaction volume of 10 μ l. The data were analyzed with LightCycler 480 SW 1.5 and Microsoft Excel 2019. Graphs were created using CorelDRAW 2022 Graphics Suite (Version 24.0.0.301).

Fig. S1. Alignment of Sanger sequencing results of translocation junctions against reference sequences. DNA sequence of the two WT- and expected as well as obtained translocation-specific junctions as detected by Sanger sequencing. Black triangles indicate the expected location of CRISPR/Cas-induced DSBs. The first two lines show the original WT sequence. The last three or four lines show the expected translocation junctions as well as their actual sequence as detected by Sanger sequencing. Deleted bases are marked by hyphens, inserted bases by white letters. The guide sequences used to target the subtelomeric region on chromosomes 1 and 5 are highlighted in orange and the corresponding protospacer adjacent motif (PAM) sequences in green. The guide sequences used to target the subcentromeric sequences of chromosome 3 are highlighted in red and the corresponding PAM sequences in blue. **(A)** DNA sequence of the two WT- and expected as well as obtained translocation-specific junctions after the first arm transfer of chromosome 3 onto chromosome 1 in line F8. **(B)** DNA sequence of the two WT- and expected as well as obtained translocation-specific junctions after the second arm transfer of chromosome 3 onto chromosome 1 in line F8. Trl-J4 (minichromosome junction) was not present in line F8. **(C)** DNA sequence of the two WT- and expected as well as obtained translocation-specific junctions after the first arm transfer of chromosome 3 onto chromosome 5 in line T8. **(D)** DNA sequence of the two WT- and expected as well as obtained translocation-specific junctions after the second arm transfer of chromosome 3 onto chromosome 1 in line T8. Trl-J4 (minichromosome junction) was not present in line T8.

Fig. S2. Alignment of F8 and T8 genome assemblies against reference genomes with the expected rearrangements. Jupiter plots showing the alignment of the F8 and T8 genome assemblies against the respective reference genomes that included the expected rearrangements, confirming the presence of the expected translocation junctions. Connections show the aligned regions of each assembly. The scaffolds are limited to those over 2 Mb in length (0.015% of the assembly). Only alignments over 5 kb in length are displayed. Crossing lines indicate rearrangements or break points in the scaffolds. **(A)** Jupiter plot showing the genome alignment of the genome assembly of line F8 (top of circle; F8 chromosomes 2, 4, 5 and fusion chromosome 3/1/3) against the reference genome (bottom of circle; Col-0 (Col) chromosomes 1-5). **(B)** Jupiter plot showing the genome alignment of the genome assembly of line T8 (top of circle; T8 chromosomes 2, 4 and fusion chromosomes 1/3 and 5/3) against the reference genome (bottom of circle; *ku70* (*ku*) chromosomes 1-5).

Fig. S3. Visualization of the translocation breakpoints detected in lines F8 and T8. Translocation breakpoints were detected by PacBio sequencing and visualized by Integrative Genomics Viewer. PacBio raw reads of lines F8 (**A**) and T8 (**B**) were aligned to the respective reference genomes that included the expected rearrangements using Minimap2. Multiple aligned reads span the reference genome at the junction site, showing consistent continuity.

Fig. S4. Differentially expressed genes (DEGs) in lines F8 and T8. Minor gene expression changes were detected after the induced chromosome number reductions. (**A**) The total number of differentially expressed genes (DEGs) for lines F8 and T8 was 88 (0.3%) and 151 (0.5%) genes, respectively. Down- and upregulated genes are shown in blue and orange bars, respectively. (**B**) Little overlap was found between the identified DEGs in lines F8 (cyan) and T8 (magenta).

Fig. S5. KEGG pathway enrichment of recognized DEGs. KEGG pathway enrichment of recognized DEGs for lines F8 (A) and T8 (B). The DEGs are mostly involved in metabolic pathways.

Fig. S6. Phenotypes of homozygous 8-chromosome plants and WT Col-0. (A) Representative images of both homozygous 8-chromosome plant lines and Col-0 plant at all scanned developmental stages. Scale bar = 6 cm. (B) Root lengths of 7-day-old seedlings of homozygous 8-chromosome lines and Col-0. Horizontal lines show medians; box limits indicate the 25th and 75th percentiles; whiskers extend to min and max values. $n = 20$ independent biological replicates, $P > 0.05$ – no statistical difference detected.

Fig. S7. PCA analyses for each phenotypic screen of homozygous 8-chromosome plants and WT Col-0. PCA plots (left) and bi-plots (right) for both homozygous 8-chromosome lines and WT Col-0 plants, based on phenotypic data obtained at 9 (A), 11 (B), 14 (C), 15 (D), 17 (E), 21 (F), 22 (G) DAS. Arrows indicate the contribution of the individual morphological traits to the principal components (the longer the arrow, the higher the contribution). The differences among plant lines are represented as centroids with ellipses representing their 95% confidence interval in PCA plots. For each phenotype scan, $n \geq 30$ independent biological replicates for F8 and T8 and $n \geq 15$ for Col-0.

Fig. S8. 3D view of PCA plot integrating phenotypic data of all seven developmental stages. [html file]

Fig. S9. Scatter-plot matrix comparing phenotypic parameters of seeds. (A) overlay of scatter-plot matrices of individual lines F8 (n = 3,970 seeds), T8 (n = 3,719 seeds) and Col-0 (n = 4,037 seeds). (B-D) scatter-plot matrices of individual lines.

Table S1. List of used spacer oligonucleotides, estimated cut positions and cutting efficiencies. Overhangs are represented by lowercase letters.

Name	Sequence 5' - 3'	Chromosome	Cut position	Mean TIDE efficiency
oMR319	agatGTTGGCTATGCAAAAATTACGCACA	3	16,212,593	65%
oMR320	ggccGTGCGTAATTTGCATAGCCAAC			
oMR226	attgGTGTTACGCCCAATTTGAGA	1	32,533,144	62%
oMR227	aaacTCTCAAATTGGGCGTAACAC			
RW291	agatGTTGTGTCATAATTGGATTATGAG	3	13,577,521	46%
RW292	ggccCTCATAATCCAATTATGACACAAC			
oMR586	agatATAGGCATGATTAATGATGATAAG	1	13,287	64%
oMR587	ggccCTTATCATCATTAATCATGCCTAT			
oMR23	attgACGTGAACTCTTTGACTTGT	5	29,471,962	64%
oMR24	aaacACAAGTCAAAGAGTTCACGT			
RW67	attgCTTAGTATAAATAAGTCTGT	3	13,596,032	69%
RW68	aaacACAGACTTATTATACTAAG			

Table S2. Annotated putative open reading frames (TAIR10) present on the minichromosomes produced to generate lines F8 and T8. No function has been reported for these genes.

Gene	Information
AT3G33187	encodes a defensin-like (DEFL) family protein
AT3G33293	myosin heavy chain-like protein myosin heavy
AT3G33393	chain-like protein hypothetical protein
AT3G33494	hypothetical protein
AT3G33528	Transducin family protein/WD-40 repeat family protein
AT3G33530	

Table S3. Translocation induction frequencies in lines F8 and T8.

Line	First arm transfer				Second arm transfer			
	Number of tested T2 pools (40 plants each)	Number of positive pools	Number of positive plants (of 40)	Translocation frequency	Number of tested T2 pools (40 plants each)	Number of positive pools	Number of positive plants (of 40)	Translocation frequency
F8	50	2	2	0.1%	60	5	1	0.2%
							1	
							2	
							1	
T8	57	1	1	0.04%	75	4	27*	0.1%**
							27*	
							1	
							1	

* The 3:1 segregation indicates that the translocation event occurred in the T1 generation during transformation.

** 4 independent events

Table S4. List of primers used for TIDE analysis, amplification of translocation junctions, TaqMan SNP markers and cloning.

Name	Sequence 5' - 3'	Amplification of
oMR391	TCACTCCACTACGATCCTGGT	F8 and T8 TIDE oMR226 fwd, F8 WT1 fwd, F8 J1 fwd, T8 WT3 fwd, T8 J3 fwd
oMR392	CACTAGCTTCTTTCACGCTTCTTG	F8 and T8 TIDE oMR226 rev, F8 WT1 rev, F8 J2 rev, T8 WT3 rev, T8 J4 fwd
oMR452	TCTGGTGATGGCACAGTACC	F8 and T8 TIDE oMR319 fwd, F8 WT2 fwd, F8 J2 fwd, T8 WT2 fwd, T8 J2 fwd
oMR453	CTCGGTGTCGTAGACGATTCT	F8 and T8 TIDE oMR319 rev, F8 WT2 rev, F8 J2 rev, T8 WT2 rev, T8 J1 rev
oMR619	GTTGCATGTAATTAGCATATGGCTA	F8 TIDE oMR586 fwd, F8 WT3 fwd, F8 J4 fwd
oMR620	GGTATTAGTGAAAAGTACGGAGGTA	F8 TIDE oMR586 rev, F8 WT3 rev, F8 J3 rev
oMR897	TGACTTTCTCCTTCTCAAGAAGAT	F8 TIDE RW291 fwd, F8 WT4 fwd, F8 J3 fwd
oMR898	CAAACATGGTACAAATTCCTTCAGT	F8 TIDE RW291 rev, F8 WT4 rev, F8 J4 rev
oMR94	GTCTTCTCCGTGATTAGATGAATCG	T8 TIDE oMR23 fwd, T8 WT1 fwd, T8 J1 fwd
oMR95	CCGACTTTTCCTGCAATCATGG	T8 TIDE oMR23 rev, T8 WT1 rev, T8 J2 rev
oMR257	TCTCTAAACCTCAGTCGATTTCTT	T8 TIDE RW67 fwd, T8 WT4 fwd, T8 J3 rev
oMR259	GAGGTTCCACAACACTCTCTC	T8 TIDE RW67 rev, T8 WT4 rev, T8 J4 rev
oMR1182	CGAGAAACACAACAATATC	Chr. 1.0 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1183	GTGGTTAACATGTTTACTTGT	Chr. 1.0 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1134	CAGTAATAGGTTGAGACTTTTGAG	Chr. 1.2 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1145	TCTCTTCCCTGTTCCGAAC	Chr. 1.2 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR976	TGCAAGAAACCAAGAATCT	Chr. 1.3 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR949	AAGAAAGCAACTGAGAAG	Chr. 1.3 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR978	CTTTCCTCAACAAATCAAATTG	Chr. 1.6 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR951	AGTCAGAATTTCTAAATCTAGG	Chr. 1.6 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1098	AGTGGATGTGAAAAAGAGT	Chr. 1.8 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1099	CAAAAATACCCAAATATCCTAC	Chr. 1.8 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR980	AGCTTCTGATCGATCAACA	Chr. 1.9 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR981	ACATGAAAGAACCTATTTGATGA	Chr. 1.9 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR954	CAATTTCTCTAATTTATTCGACTTTTG	Chr. 1.12 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR955	CGGTCCATTTGAAAGCAG	Chr. 1.12 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1068	CAAATTTTGTATCGCTGTTTTAAC	Chr. 1.14 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1069	GGATAAAAGTTCCTTAAGAATTAAC	Chr. 1.14 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1100	GAGAAAGATCGATGGTTCAAT	Chr. 1.18 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1101	GTCTAATGGATTACCGAATTG	Chr. 1.18 Mb SNP marker rev

oMR984	TAAACCAAAGAGGTAAGAGC	Chr. 120 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR985	GTTTTGTCTTTAAAATGTTTCAGC	Chr. 120 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1102	ACTATTTGACCGTTAATAGGATG	Chr. 122 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1103	CCAATTTGGGATAAACAATAACTAT	Chr. 122 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR986	CTTTCCAGCTTCGATGAC	Chr. 123 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR987	GCCCGTGTTTCAAAGATG	Chr. 123 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR962	GAAAGGTCAAATTGGAGATCT	Chr. 126 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR963	GCTTATCCTAAAACCAACAAG	Chr. 126 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1104	CATTTGTTGGTTAGTTATAAGTC	Chr. 128 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1105	CTTTTCTGATCATGTTATAGATAC	Chr. 128 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1106	CAAGCCTCATCAACCAAAT	Chr. 130 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1107	TCTTAATCCTAAGCTGATGTTTATG	Chr. 130 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1184	TTAGATCTGGTACTGAAACG	Chr. 132 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1185	TAACTCCATAGACGATAATCAC	Chr. 132 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR772	GTGACGTTGACAATAAGTG	Chr. 30 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR773	TCTAAAGGTCTCTCCATCAT	Chr. 30 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1124	TTATTCATATTTTGTACTTCTCC	Chr. 32 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1125	AATTTGAATATCGGCCAAC	Chr. 32 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR377	CGAAGACCTGACAGAAATC	Chr. 33 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR378	AAGATCCGTAGAGTTTTACATAC	Chr. 33 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR495	AAGAATATTACTTGTCTTCTAGG	Chr. 35 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR496	TATATTGTAGGATGCTTCTC	Chr. 35 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR440	GAATGTTGTTTTAATGTGGC	Chr. 38 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR441	ATTCAGACAGTAATGACTCA	Chr. 38 Mb SNP marker rev
RW543	CGACCTAGCAACCCGAAATA	Chr. 310 Mb SNP marker fwd
RW544	TTTAGGACCAAGGAGAACCA	Chr. 310 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR552	TAACAACACTGGGTCAAC	Chr. 311 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR553	AGAAAACCTCTTCCATTCTG	Chr. 311 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1176	CTAATTAACGGCCGTTAATAG	Chr. 313 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1177	ATGGGGAAGGATAGGTGT	Chr. 313 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1178	CCACATAAACTTAAAAGTAATCGTT	Chr. 316 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1179	TAAGAGCGATTACGGTCC	Chr. 316 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR497	ATCGTAACTTTTTGTTAACTTTG	Chr. 318 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR498	ATTCTTTCAGACGATTCTATC	Chr. 318 Mb SNP marker rev
RW709	GAATGATAAACCCCTCGAACC	Chr. 319 Mb SNP marker fwd
RW710	CTTTGAATGGATGCAATGGC	Chr. 319 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR355	GTTATACTTCAATCGAGTTGA	Chr. 321 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR356	CTGACCTGATATGTTGTATG	Chr. 321 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR519	GATCAATCGAGCTTTCAG	Chr. 323 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR500	CTTGCAAAAGTTTAGTTCTC	Chr. 323 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR780	GGAGAGTCTCGAAGGATAT	Chr. 325 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR781	CACTAATCTCAAGTAAAGTCTCT	Chr. 325 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1072	GTAATTATATACTAAGTTAACCGGC	Chr. 47 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1073	GCTTGGAGTTCTCAACATATATG	Chr. 47 Mb SNP marker rev
RW421	TCCTTACATTGGTCTACCT	Chr. 49 Mb SNP marker fwd
RW422	CAACTCGTTAGCAAGACT	Chr. 49 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1074	TGGCTTGGTTAGAAGAAATT	Chr. 412 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1095	AAAGTGTCCGATGCAATT	Chr. 412 Mb SNP marker rev
RW499	CGCAAAAATTGTCAAAGTTGC	Chr. 413 Mb SNP marker fwd
RW500	GTGGCCGGATTTAAGTCT	Chr. 413 Mb SNP marker rev
RW374	TAAGTGAAGTGGGTACCAAG	Chr. 415 Mb SNP marker fwd
RW375	GCCTCTTTATATCTGCTTTC	Chr. 415 Mb SNP marker rev
RW501	GATTCAGCAAGCAAACCTCTCA	Chr. 418 Mb SNP marker fwd
RW502	GTTTCATGCTGTAGTTGAAGAGC	Chr. 418 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1130	CAAACACGAGACAGTATATC	Chr. 420 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1143	GTGTTGCTTTTGTGGATG	Chr. 420 Mb SNP marker rev
RW503	TACCTTCATTTTGAAAGGG	Chr. 421 Mb SNP marker fwd
RW504	ACAAGAGTTTGTTCAGACGA	Chr. 421 Mb SNP marker rev

oMR806	ATTGTGTCATTCGTCGTC	Chr. 5 0 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR807	ACCATCTTCTATCATGATGAG	Chr. 5 0 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR810	TGACATTTCCGGTATCTGTG	Chr. 5 2 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR811	GTATCACATAAGTCAAGGCTA	Chr. 5 2 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1108	CCACATCAATAAACATTGGAC	Chr. 5 4 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1109	TCCTCTTGACATATGGTTCTTG	Chr. 5 4 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR840	GTAAATGAAAACGTAGTTGC	Chr. 5 6 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR841	AGTTACAAGTTTAAAGTCCCT	Chr. 5 6 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1110	GCAAAGACATATCCGCAG	Chr. 5 8 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1123	GTAAGTTTTTAAAAGGCTGT	Chr. 5 8 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR814	CGTTGAATCTTATAATTGTAAGAGC	Chr. 5 9 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR815	TGACCAACTTTAGCATTTGA	Chr. 5 9 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR855	AATGAAGTTCTGACACACG	Chr. 5 11 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR856	TGCTGATGGAGACTTCATT	Chr. 5 11 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1112	TGCATTAAGTAAATTCATGTAGTT	Chr. 5 16 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1113	AGCATATGTTCTCATTTCTTGAG	Chr. 5 16 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR844	GCGGGTCTAAATTTGTTA	Chr. 5 17 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR819	GCTCTAATAGCATTAGATCC	Chr. 5 17 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR877	TTGATGAGTCGATTCAGTA	Chr. 5 20 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR879	TAGTTGGAGTCCATAGAAG	Chr. 5 20 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1126	ATGTTAGATGGTATTGGTTGGT	Chr. 5 22 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1127	GCCAAGTTATCTTCTCAAAGTA	Chr. 5 22 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR883	CACAAGTAGAGATAGATTTTCAA	Chr. 5 23 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR884	GGTCTGACAATATTCTTAACC	Chr. 5 23 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR824	CATTGAAGTTATGTTGGTTCG	Chr. 5 26 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR825	AGGATTTAATGTTGTGTTGAC	Chr. 5 26 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1138	TCGAGTAATCTAACATTAGGAAT	Chr. 5 28 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1139	CTTACGTTTGATTGTGTAAC	Chr. 5 28 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR1190	GGCATTGTGCTCAAATCT	Chr. 5 29 Mb SNP marker fwd
oMR1191	ATCTTGCTTCTGTAGCTAAATT	Chr. 5 29 Mb SNP marker rev
oMR899	GCATGCAAGCTTCAGCTTGCCAAC	Amplification of kanamycin resistance cassette
oMR900	AGTGCCAAGCTTGACAACCTTAATAACACATTG	
oMR577	TGACGAACGTTGTCGAAACC	Amplification of ttLb-Cas12a-i ORF
oMR752	TGGAGTTGTTGACTTGATTGATTTG	
oMR790	CTAGTCAAGCTTGATCTAGTAACATAGATGACACCGC	Amplification of hygromycin resistance cassette
oMR791	CGATCGAAGCTTGAACCGCAACGTTGAAGGAG	

Table S5. Overview of used FISH probes.

Probe color	Description
Yellow	BAC probes specific to both chromosome 1 arms
Blue	Single-copy oligo FISH probes specific to the long arm of chromosome 3
Magenta	Single-copy oligo FISH probes specific to the short arm of chromosome 3
Green	BAC probes specific to chromosome 5

Table S6. Overview of the sequence and position of the SNP markers used. SNPs between Col-0 and Ler-1 are marked in red. The oligonucleotides were modified by adding a fluorophore (HEX/FAM) at the 5' end and a quencher (BHQ1) at the 3' end. The positions are based on Naish *et al.* 2021 (13).

Name	Sequence 5' - 3'	SNP position
Chr. 1		
Chr. 1 0 Mb Col	[HEX]ATATACAGCTTCAGC G TAAACCAGATACTC[BHQ1]	453,793
Chr. 1 0 Mb Ler	[FAM]ATATACAGCTTCAGC C TAAACCAGATACTC[BHQ1]	
Chr. 1 2 Mb Col	[HEX]GACAGCTGCTTGTT C CGTAGATTCTCTG[BHQ1]	1,997,036
Chr. 1 2 Mb Ler	[FAM]GACAGCTGCTTGTT T CGTAGATTCTCTG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 1 3 Mb Col	[HEX]CTAACCTCGA T CGGAGTTCCAAT[BHQ1]	3,015,107
Chr. 1 3 Mb Ler	[FAM]CTAACCTCGA C CGGAGTTCCAAT[BHQ1]	
Chr. 1 6 Mb Col	[HEX]CAGAGATACACAT T TATGAACATACCCG[BHQ1]	6,003,969
Chr. 1 6 Mb Ler	[FAM]CAGAGATACACAT C TATGAACATACCCG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 1 8 Mb Col	[HEX]AACCTAATCATT G TCCAACCTTATCGAG[BHQ1]	7,918,497
Chr. 1 8 Mb Ler	[FAM]AACCTAATCATT G TCCAACCTTATCGAG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 1 9 Mb Col	[HEX]CGATGTTAAAGTCTAC C CCTGGTGTACA[BHQ1]	9,025,881
Chr. 1 9 Mb Ler	[FAM]CGATGTTAAAGTCTAC T CCTGGTGTACA[BHQ1]	
Chr. 1 12 Mb Col	[FAM]TCCGTTCCGGG C CAGACCAAAT[BHQ1]	12,044,412
Chr. 1 12 Mb Ler	[HEX]TCCGTTCCGGG T CAGACCAAAT[BHQ1]	
Chr. 1 14 Mb Col	[HEX]CCGTATTGGGTCTA A AGACCATTTTCGTT[BHQ1]	14,178,790
Chr. 1 14 Mb Ler	[FAM]CCGTATTGGGTCTA T AGACCATTTTCGTT[BHQ1]	
Chr. 1 18 Mb Col	[HEX]CTCGTGATCGT G TTCGATCCCGATG[BHQ1]	18,098,683
Chr. 1 18 Mb Ler	[FAM]CTCGTGATCGT C TTCGATCCCGATG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 1 20 Mb Col	[HEX]CCTCTAATAGCA A TTTCTCAGAGAAGTCAG[BHQ1]	20,145,743
Chr. 1 20 Mb Ler	[FAM]CCTCTAATAGCA G TTTCTCAGAGAAGTCAG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 1 22 Mb Col	[HEX]ATGGTACACAAAA A TCTCATGAGTCATGGA[BHQ1]	22,144,602
Chr. 1 22 Mb Ler	[FAM]ATGGTACACAAAA C TCTCATGAGTCATGGA[BHQ1]	
Chr. 1 23 Mb Col	[HEX]TCACATCCC A TGCTTACTGAAGTCTTAGG[BHQ1]	23,129,710
Chr. 1 23 Mb Ler	[FAM]TCACATCCC A TGCTTACTGAAGTCTTAGG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 1 26 Mb Col	[HEX]ATTATTACCAAT C ACACTTCGAGCAGTGGG[BHQ1]	26,123,185
Chr. 1 26 Mb Ler	[FAM]ATTATTACCAAT T ACACTTCGAGCAGTGGG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 1 28 Mb Col	[HEX]CTTATGGCGCCACTAG T TCTCAAATTAAT[BHQ1]	28,104,281
Chr. 1 28 Mb Ler	[FAM]CTTATGGCGCCACTAG A TCTCAAATTAAT[BHQ1]	
Chr. 1 30 Mb Col	[HEX]CCGACCTAAATC G CCACAAAAATGTCATG[BHQ1]	30,041,026
Chr. 1 30 Mb Ler	[FAM]CCGACCTAAATC A CCACAAAAATGTCATG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 1 32 Mb Col	[HEX]CTAAGAATGCTCAT C GAAGAGCTTCACTGG[BHQ1]	32,104,136
Chr. 1 32 Mb Ler	[FAM]CTAAGAATGCTCAT T GAAGAGCTTCACTGG[BHQ1]	

Chr. 3		
Chr. 3 0 Mb Col	[HEX]TGACACTTCTTGTACCTCTTAAAGCATG[BHQ1]	11,125
Chr. 3 0 Mb Ler	[FAM]TGACACTTCTTGTGACCTCTTAAAGCATG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 3 2 Mb Col	[HEX]ATCATGAGTTTATCTTCGACTTGTTCACTC[BHQ1]	1,999,637
Chr. 3 2 Mb Ler	[FAM]ATCATGAGTTTATCTTGGACTTGTTCACTC[BHQ1]	
Chr. 3 3 Mb Col	[HEX]CCTTTCACTAACTATAACGCATGCGGTTTC[BHQ1]	3,284,961
Chr. 3 3 Mb Ler	[FAM]CCTTTCACTAACTATAACGCATGCGGTTTC[BHQ1]	
Chr. 3 5 Mb Col	[HEX]TGAAACACGAGCAGCCAGATCT[BHQ1]	5,702,429
Chr. 3 5 Mb Ler	[FAM]TGAAACACGGCAGCCAGATCT[BHQ1]	
Chr. 3 8 Mb Col	[HEX]TCATCAATCGACGAACTGTCACACT[BHQ1]	8,882,578
Chr. 3 8 Mb Ler	[FAM]TCATCAATCGGCGAACTGTCACACT[BHQ1]	
Chr. 3 10 Mb Col	[HEX]AGATTTGTCACCGTCAACCTAAGA[BHQ1]	10,522,895
Chr. 3 10 Mb Ler	[FAM]AGATTTGTCACTGTCAACCTAAGA[BHQ1]	
Chr. 3 11 Mb Col	[HEX]CATCTGGGCTCTGTCCTTCATACTG[BHQ1]	11,588,327
Chr. 3 11 Mb Ler	[FAM]CATCTGGGCTATGTCCTTCATACTG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 3 13 Mb Col	[HEX]GAATCGCTAACCGCGGTTAAACTTAATCT[BHQ1]	13,186,298
Chr. 3 13 Mb Ler	[FAM]GAATCGCTAACCGCAGTTAAACTTAATCT[BHQ1]	
Chr. 3 16 Mb Col	[HEX]CGAGATCTCATTAAAGCGGACGAGTAATGAC[BHQ1]	16,267,897
Chr. 3 16 Mb Ler	[FAM]CGAGATCTCATTAAAGCCGACGAGTAATGAC[BHQ1]	
Chr. 3 18 Mb Col	[HEX]CATTAGCAAGTATTAACATACTTTCACGGA[BHQ1]	18,839,699
Chr. 3 18 Mb Ler	[FAM]CATTAGCAAGTATTAACATACTTTCACGGA[BHQ1]	
Chr. 3 19 Mb Col	[HEX]AAGAACCACATGATCCATTATGGAAT[BHQ1]	19,217,154
Chr. 3 19 Mb Ler	[FAM]AAGAACCACATGATTCATTATGGAAT[BHQ1]	
Chr. 3 21 Mb Col	[HEX]CCAGAACTTAATGTGTTATGCTCAGACAGC[BHQ1]	21,789,543
Chr. 3 21 Mb Ler	[FAM]CCAGAACTTAATGATTATGCTCAGACAGC[BHQ1]	
Chr. 3 23 Mb Col	[HEX]CCAAATCTCCGGTTTACCAATCATA[BHQ1]	23,271,767
Chr. 3 23 Mb Ler	[FAM]CCAAATCTCCGGCTTACCAATCATA[BHQ1]	
Chr. 3 25 Mb Col	[HEX]CTTCTGCACCGCAAAACAAA TCAAGA[BHQ1]	25,732,474
Chr. 3 25 Mb Ler	[FAM]CTTCTGCACCGCAAAACCAAATCAAGA[BHQ1]	
Chr. 4		
Chr. 4 7 Mb Col	[HEX]CATACTCTAATAGTCCCCCTCAAGCTTGAG[BHQ1]	7,095,983
Chr. 4 7 Mb Ler	[FAM]CATACTCTAATAGCCCCCTCAAGCTTGAG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 4 9 Mb Col	[HEX]CACCCGATCTGACCCGACA[BHQ1]	9,887,504
Chr. 4 9 Mb Ler	[FAM]CACCCGATCCGACCCGACA[BHQ1]	
Chr. 4 12 Mb Col	[HEX]CAAGTGACCGAATTTGAACTCAAATTTCTC[BHQ1]	12,165,996
Chr. 4 12 Mb Ler	[FAM]CAAGTGACCAATTTGAACTCAAATTTCTC[BHQ1]	
Chr. 4 13 Mb Col	[HEX]ACAAAAGCCGGTGTGCGAAA[BHQ1]	13,352,478
Chr. 4 13 Mb Ler	[FAM]ACAAAAGCCCGTGTGCGAAA[BHQ1]	
Chr. 4 15 Mb Col	[HEX]CAGCTCATTTCCATCAGATTCGAATGTGA[BHQ1]	15,025,551
Chr. 4 15 Mb Ler	[FAM]CAGCTCATTTCCATCATATTCGAATGTGA[BHQ1]	
Chr. 4 18 Mb Col	[HEX]ATAAAACACCAAACAAGTCAATGAGACA[BHQ1]	18,039,934
Chr. 4 18 Mb Ler	[FAM]ATAAAACACCAAACAAGTCAATGAGACA[BHQ1]	
Chr. 4 20 Mb Col	[HEX]CTTTTCTGCTCTTTCCACTGAAATGATTG[BHQ1]	19,999,706
Chr. 4 20 Mb Ler	[FAM]CTTTTCTGCTCTTTCCCTGAAATGATTG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 4 21 Mb Col	[HEX]TCAAACCTCATCTGAGATTTTCATGGAA[BHQ1]	21,392,775
Chr. 4 21 Mb Ler	[FAM]TCAAACCTCATCTAGATTTTCATGGAA[BHQ1]	

Chr. 5		
Chr. 5 0 Mb Col	[HEX]AGGACTTCATAACCCG G CAAGTAAGACA[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 0 Mb Ler		0,003,413
	[FAM]AGGACTTCATAACCCG A CAAGTAAGACA[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 2 Mb Col	[HEX]TGACTAGAGTCTCAT C CCAGAGTATTGC[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 2 Mb Ler		2,706,913
	[FAM]TGACTAGAGTCTCAT A CCAGAGTATTGC[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 4 Mb Col	[HEX]CATAATGTTGCATAGCACT T GTACCCCTGT[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 4 Mb Ler		4,019,359
	[FAM]CATAATGTTGCATAGCACT C GTACCCCTGT[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 6 Mb Col	[HEX]CTGGAATAACACTA A TAATTCCGAGCAAG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 6 Mb Ler		6,005,482
	[FAM]CTGGAATAACACTA G TAATTCCGAGCAAG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 8 Mb Col	[HEX]ACCCTTGTGTATGT T ACCTATAGATCTGGGGAT[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 8 Mb Ler		8,047,552
	[FAM]ACCCTTGTGTATGT C ACCTATAGATCTGGGGAT[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 9 Mb Col	[HEX]ATACACTGCAAAA G CATGCATTGTGATTCA[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 9 Mb Ler		9,001,846
	[FAM]ATACACTGCAAAA C CATGCATTGTGATTCA[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 11 Mb Col	[HEX]TCTATCTTGGAT T GGCTGCTCCG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 11 Mb Ler		11,527,481
	[FAM]TCTATCTTGGAT C GGCTGCTCCG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 16 Mb Col	[HEX]CTAACCCAATGACC A AATCTGCTAGTTCGT[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 16 Mb Ler		16,013,804
	[FAM]CTAACCCAATGACC T AATCTGCTAGTTCGT[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 17 Mb Col	[HEX]CTATCGTACACTAAA C TACTAGTGACCA[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 17 Mb Ler		17,460,575
	[FAM]CTATCGTACACTAAA G TACTAGTGACCA[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 20 Mb Col	[HEX]CAGAAGCTCTGT A GTCCTGCTA[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 20 Mb Ler		20,553,770
	[FAM]CAGAAGCTCTGT A CTCCTGCTA[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 22 Mb Col	[HEX]CACAAGACTGAT T TCGCTGGCTCT[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 22 Mb Ler		22,000,333
	[FAM]CACAAGACTGAT A TCGCTGGCTCT[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 23 Mb Col	[HEX]GAAACTGCAAGG A TACCTGCTTC[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 23 Mb Ler		23,504,394
	[FAM]GAAACTGCAAGG G TACCTGCTTC[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 26 Mb Col	[HEX]CGCTCCGTGAGAGA A ATGGTACTG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 26 Mb Ler		26,473,933
	[FAM]CGCTCCGTGAGAGAT A TGGTACTG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 28 Mb Col	[HEX]GACAACACTCAGTT T TATTAAGCGATTG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 28 Mb Ler		28,007,813
	[FAM]GACAACACTCAGTT C TATTAAGCGATTG[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 29 Mb Col	[HEX]TCAACTTCTAGAGCACT A TCATTGGCCTC[BHQ1]	
Chr. 5 29 Mb Ler		29,059,229
	[FAM]TCAACTTCTAGAGCACT G TTCATTGGCCTC[BHQ1]	

Data S1. (separate file)

Source Data for Figs. S2 and S3 (Sniffles2 output file).

Data S2. (separate file)

Source Data for Figs. 3a-c, 4, Figs. S6b, S7, S8 and S9 (PCA analysis, fertility analysis, recombination analysis, root length analysis and seed phenotyping,).

Data S3. (separate file)

QUAST report of PacBio sequencing for lines F8 and T8.

Data S4. (separate file)

QUAST report of genome assemblies for lines F8 and T8.